

Work -Life Balance of Software Engineers in Selected IT Companies in Chennai District

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Abstract: A changing economy and an aging workforce can join together to create an environment where competent employees who are unhappy in their current situations are motivated. Engaged workforce is 50% more productive than an unengaged. Most of HR people feel engagement of employees is important for the success of the organization. Employee engagement is a critical aspect in today's competitive marketplace. Work life balance is increasingly important for engagement and also an important content of employee satisfaction. The expression Work - life balance was first used in 1986 in US to explain the unhealthy life choices that many people made, they chose to neglect other areas of their life like family , peer group in favor of work related goals. The data pertaining to the study has been collected among the soft engineers of selected IT companies to analyze the Work-life balance. They have been given a well-structured questionnaire to give out their responses with assured confidentiality of the information. Percentage analysis, Simple Ranking and Henry Garrett Ranking has been used to analyze the data collected.

Key Words: *Work Life Balance, Engagement, satisfaction, Software Engineers.*

Introduction

The term Work Life Balance (WLB) is attracted by all including the individuals and Corporate all over the world. Work Life Balance (WLB) is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement between the multiple roles of a person's life. It is a person's control over the responsibilities between their workplace, family, friends and self. It is a comfortable state of equilibrium achieved between employee's primary priorities at their work place and at their private life. There are various people like family members, friends, supervisors, peer group and others involved in every person's life. The support gained from them will play a

key role in leading a comfortable life journey. The challenge of WLB is rising to the top of many employees. Employees are placing more importance on quality of work life (QWL) and seek for flexibility so they would be able to balance their work and personal commitments. The availability of technology anywhere which assists in the connectivity of people has delineated the boundaries between work and personal life.

Literature Review

Gibson, (2006) offered two explanations regarding the interconnectedness of work and life in the organizational setting: (1) the compensation effect implies that employees tend to compensate for low work or personal life satisfaction by seeking contentment in the other domain; and (2) the spillover view that indicates that job satisfaction spills over into one's work life and vice versa.

Helen De Cieri et. al. (2005) argue that an organizations need to attract and retain valued employees in a highly competitive labour market is a strong motivating factor for increased organizational awareness and action with regard to implementation and management of WLB strategies. While some achievements have been made over the years, there remain substantial challenges for the uptake and management of WLB strategies.

R. Baral and S. Bhargava (2011) have analyzed that family-friendliness of employers in India have been reflected in various welfare provisions which has been a matter of concern for employers since industrialization. With time, the scope and coverage of such initiatives have broadened and have become more individual growth and family well-being oriented.

Rakesh Yadav, (2011) analyzed that factors such as absence of personal life, physical strains, unscheduled work hours were affecting the attrition from HR perspective which could be minimized by giving extra break to employees who work continuously in night shift for five days, compensating workers with wellness programs and stress busters and aligning employees holidays with the clients' holidays.

Statement of the problem

Since previous research has shown that organizational culture influences employee behavior and productivity, one should assume interpersonal relationships among colleagues also directly impact behavior and productivity. Healthy organizational cultures that emphasize collaborative relationships should therefore produce more productive and satisfied employees, who feel their individual needs are being met. Focusing on the communications industry, compiled of businesses that widely disseminate information, this study examined the employee work-life balance within healthy organizational cultures by considering the influence on collaborative relationships helping employees maintain active lifestyles outside the office. It then aimed to determine possible organizational policies that lead to enhanced employee satisfaction and commitment.

Objective of the study

- To study the perception of employees towards factors affecting Work-life balance.

Research methodology

The present study was carried out in IT sector, chennai by. A sample of 100 employees was selected for gathering primary data. The respondents are working as software engineers. To carry out the study in a more accurate and easier way, convenience sampling method was adopted. Both primary and secondary data have been used to draw appropriate conclusions. The primary data was collected by using questionnaire method. The collected data had been analyzed by using Percentage analysis, Simple Ranking Analysis, Henry Garrett Ranking Analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table No1: General Profile of Respondents

Factors	Classification	Number	Percentage
Age	20-25	24	24
	26-30	53	53
	31-35	10	10
	Above 35	13	13
Marital Status	Single	48	48
	Married	51	51
	Separated	01	01
Experience	Below 2 yrs	16	16
	3-5 yrs	16	16
	6-8yrs	12	12
	Above 9 yrs	56	56

Source: Primary Data

In the Table 1, 53% of the respondents are come under the age category of 26-30. 51% of the respondents are married and 1% come under the category of separated. 56% of the respondents are having above 9 years of work experience.

Table No.2

Frequency of Respondents facing difficulty in balancing personal life and work life

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	74	74
No	26	26

Source: Primary Data

The table no.2 shows that 74% of the respondents face difficulty in balancing personal life and work life.

Table No.3

Simple Ranking Analysis: Perceived Factors that affect Work Life Balance

S.No	Factors	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	T.S	order
1.	Support from top management	12	9	16	13	13	11	8	9	4	5	623	III
2.	Support from colleagues	14	14	6	10	9	3	16	10	8	10	574	IV
3.	Organizational change	5	4	9	4	7	16	13	11	17	14	440	X
4.	Working hours	19	18	11	12	12	8	6	4	4	6	689	I
5.	Managerial style	10	12	18	16	11	12	7	5	7	2	660	II
6.	Family support	12	6	8	7	11	10	9	16	12	9	520	VI
7.	Work overload	7	10	6	12	9	7	14	10	13	12	505	VII
8.	Work life conflict	5	13	11	10	8	11	9	12	9	12	530	V
9.	Psychological distress	12	5	7	6	7	11	8	12	14	18	475	IX
10.	Personal financial problems	4	9	8	10	13	11	10	11	12	12	499	VIII

Source : Primary data

From Table No.3, it can be inferred that the factor working time is perceived by most and having the greatest impact on Work-Life Balance with score of 686. Managerial style stands the next most influencing factor on Work-Life Balance with score of 659, followed by the ‘support from top management’ having a score of 625. Support from colleagues and work life conflict are the other consecutive factors that are considered to be strongly affecting work-life balance. The diagram represents the perceived factors and its total score for easy understanding.

Table No.4 Henry Garrett Ranking Analysis: Work -Life Balance Dimensions.

Dimensions	Items	Mean Score	Dimension Total Mean Score	Ranking
Personal Health	I get adequate sleep	57.71	179.85	I
	I get enough time to exercise, hobbies and sports	36.33		
	I do not suffer from health issues	43.51		
	I am mentally and physically active	42.22		
Family and Peer Group	I get adequate time to spend with family and friends	49.41	148.31	II
	I am able to meet my home demands	47.14		
	I get adequate time for personal responsibilities	51.74		
Organizational Relationship	I get enough time to interact with colleagues and Management	53.65	143.42	III
	I am able to build strong relationship with Colleagues and Management	47.42		
	I am able to express myself effectively	42.33		
Work environment	Achievement of targets	51.45	142.80	IV
	Enjoying the Job	49.11		
	Skill enhancement	42.22		

Source: Primary data

Henry Garrett Ranking Technique has been used to rank the dimensions. The study deals with only four dimensions and the total mean score has been ranked. It is inferred that Personal health has been ranked first with total mean score of 179.85 followed by Family & peer group with total mean score of 148.31 then Organizational relationship (total mean score is 143.42) has been ranked third and finally Work environment obtains fourth rank (total mean score is 142.80). When we need to discuss about items that represent highest mean score in each dimension, in the first dimension "*Personal Health*" the item adequate sleep get the maximum score of 57.71 , the second dimension "*Family & peer group*" adequate time for personal responsibilities gets the highest score of 51.74, third dimension "*Organisational*

Relationship” enough time to interact with colleagues and Management gets the highest score of 53.65 and the fourth dimension “*Work environment*” achievement of targets get the greatest score of 51.46.

Suggestion

Awareness regarding work life balance will improve employees’ performance. It is the responsibility of the organization to help the employees to overcome the difficulties they face in the aspect of WLB because employees are the important asset for an organization. In the study made the least scored item is time spent for exercise, hobbies and sport (mean score is 36.35). So the organization can make arrangements for creating awareness among the employees regarding the importance of exercise and sport for their physical health by arranging some health camp or lecture / awareness program by a doctor.

Conclusion

In the present scenario many organizations are trying to bring in work life balance of the employees by taking care of the factors like working from home, flexi time and swap in order to retain talent, enhance quality of work and to keep the employees happy. The flexibility of work alleviates stress and helps in better time management. Employees living with joint families are more comfortable when compared to those from nuclear families. Work-life balance requires cooperation and coordination at national, governmental, organizational, as well as the individual level.

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